

E-RIHS IP

European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science IMPLEMENTATION Phase

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D6.2 Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication strategy of E-RIHS ERIC

Authors: Benassi Laura, Manconi Silvia, Chaban Antonina, Carmona Paula, Castillejo Marta, Iachello Silvia, Andrews Miriam, Fremout Wim, Padfield Joseph, Striova Jana

ABSTRACT

The document presents the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) strategy for the upcoming E-RIHS ERIC. It highlights the importance of effective communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities in European projects, aligning with the European Commission's framework. The strategy focuses on organizing communication activities, learning from past experiences, defining the vision and objectives, identifying the audience and key messages, branding, promoting hashtags, and utilizing various tools and channels. Furthermore, it emphasizes the significance of open science, citizen science, and the exploitation strategy for long-term sustainability, detailing mechanisms to facilitate effective exploitation, mapping and monitoring innovation, specialized management, IPR support systems, data services, engaging the user community, training, and funding. The strategy also encompasses monitoring and reporting DEC activities to evaluate the RI's performance and impact.

It will be a live document that must be revised periodically.

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Responsible Author	Name: Laura Benassi	Email: laura.benassi@cnr.it	

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviations	Expansion
CC	Creative Common
CLO	Central Liason Office for Innovation
CMS	Content Management System
CON	Communication Officers Network
CS	Citizen Science
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HS	Heritage Science
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI(s)	Key Performance Indicator(s)
NN(s)	National Node(s)
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDSAB	Regional Development Strategies Advisory Board
RI(s)	Research Infrastructure(s)
TTO	Technology Transfer Office

INTRODUCTION

European Research Infrastructures (RIs) are an essential pillar of the EU's economic growth. RIs contribute to key scientific and technological discoveries and considerably impact other elements such as social cohesion, cultural changes, and citizens' well-being.

In the "Communication Indicators" paper (2022), the European Commission defined the framework for the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities that must be adopted in the European projects. The paper summarized the context and meaning of these strategic activities in a table to underline that communication is the way to promote your action and results; dissemination is to make results public, and exploitation is to make concrete use of results.

The same definitions have been adopted by the ESFRI research infrastructures. Entered in the ESFRI Roadmap in 2016, E-RIHS is a distributed research infrastructure in the field of heritage science that offers physical, remote, and virtual access to its services and expertise, mainly based on an excellence basis.

Following the framework defined by the European Commission, deliverable D6.2 will plan the E-RIHS communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, will track the opportunities, and will monitor its impact on global societal and economic challenges.

COMMUNICATION

1.1 How the communication is organized in the other RIs

Between 2019 and 2022, different surveys (EMMRI, RIV-VIS, IPERION HS) analyzed the state-of-the-art of communication in the RIs, providing an overview of available tools and resources. The surveys were conducted partially by using the websites as data sources and partially by interviewing communication officers and managers of research infrastructures working in different fields, distributed mainly in Europe.

The RI-VIS analysis featured that many research infrastructures do not monitor communication activities or establish KPIs, lack dedicated communication staff, and when present the staff is not sufficient. They do not prioritize social media, and other media (newsletters, videos, service catalogues, etc.) are not considered relevant. In general, the stakeholders prefer in-person interactions.

The IPERION HS survey corroborated the RI-VIS data and provided additional insights. According to the survey results, communication in RIs is mainly handled by scientists without specific training and follows no organized workflow. In distributed RIs, communication typically occurs at the central level and does not involve National Nodes (from now on, NNs). Only in a few cases, collaboration exists between the Central Hub and NNs.

Most of the interviewed communication officers highlighted the shortage of personnel and resources with respect of the huge number of activities to be supported (training, conferences, research results, internal and external communications, and participation in EU projects).

The preferred channels used are the website, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, and to a lesser extent Facebook.

In a recent webinar (YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=e3fkUIVRoNY>), Lorenzo Merignati, professor at the University Bicocca in Milan, states that the secret word for good communication within the research infrastructures is MARCOM, which combines marketing with communication strategies and activities strategically.

E-RIHS is building its strategy for DEC activities on the past experiences of its scientific community and the current experience of other research infrastructures.

1.2 What we learnt from the past

The E-RIHS community has been working together for many years. Based on the previous experiences collected in the E-RIHS PP and IPERION HS projects, E-RIHS inherited the best practices experimented with in different international contexts and is reinforcing its own communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy making it suitable for an evolving situation.

Deliverable D6.2 presents the objectives, messages, audience, channels and tools, and KPIs that will be adopted by the E-RIHS ERIC communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy.

1.3 Our communication strategy: vision and objectives

E-RIHS mission is to deliver integrated access to expertise, data and technologies for protecting heritage and to promote innovation in the field of heritage science. E-RIHS combines science with innovation and has a strong, potential impact on society and the economy. In this context, it is fundamental for E-RIHS to embrace a holistic approach to communication to effectively engage the public and make its impact effective on society, building a collaborative and interdisciplinary environment around the common issue of the protection of world heritage.

One of the E-RIHS pillars is “communicating with people” and not to people, having interactions with them both online and in-person to develop long-term relationships, and creating consistent pathways to share the E-RIHS outcomes.

The objectives of the E-RIHS communication strategy are:

- support internal communications to strengthen the commitment to the research infrastructure
- create a collaborative environment at a global level for the protection of heritage
- strengthen the E-RIHS presence in the RIs environment and the E-RIHS cohesion in the heritage science community
- increase the visibility of E-RIHS by communicating scientific results
- enhance the impact of E-RIHS outcomes by disseminating and translating them into actionable insights for stakeholders, including practitioners and policy-makers
- engage the target audience and the public
- involve users and new communities.

The E-RIHS communication combines the SMART strategy with the C-style. SMART stands for specific, measurable, achievable, relevant and time-bound; C-style means a clear, coordinated, consistent and creative style.

The E-RIHS communication activities are coordinated by a E-RIHS Communication Officer at the Central Hub and managed together with the Communication Officers Network that includes one representative per country. The workflow is described in the E-RIHS IP deliverable D2.5.

1.4 Audience and messages

“Where Is My Audience?” is one of the most critical questions a research infrastructure needs to ask itself. To establish a strong connection and effectively communicate with the E-RIHS audience, it is essential to comprehend their unique characteristics. By aligning messages and utilizing suitable channels, E-RIHS can successfully engage with people who have diverse attributes including age, occupation, hobbies, and more.

Figure 1 E-RIHS targeted audience

E-RIHS can target its current audience by analyzing:

1. The E-RIHS participation in initiatives and projects at international, European and national level, as illustrated in the table below:

LEVEL	MEANS	EXAMPLES	AUDIENCE
GLOBAL	Participation in pan-European initiatives	Resinfra project, Antecipa, etc.	researchers, academia, other RIs, policymakers and funders, etc.
EUROPEAN	Participation in European projects and other long-term initiatives - letters of cooperation	SSHOC, ARCHE, MoU with DiSSCO, OpenAIRE, etc.	other EU RIs, researchers, ESFRI and EU policymakers and funders, etc.
NATIONAL	Participation in projects and initiatives	H2IOSC (Next generation EU - Italy), etc.	E-RIHS NNs, National RIs, researchers, national policymakers and funders, professionals, etc.

2. The web presence (website and social media)

Thousands of people follow the E-RIHS website and social media. Mainly, they are researchers at the early or medium stage of their careers looking for research and training opportunities. The E-RIHS web presence catches researchers from all continents, with some differences depending on the social media and the initiatives.

3. The audience of the training initiatives (online and in person)

The online audience of HS Academy consists of thousands of people who attend the events live on the Zoom platform or watch them later on the E-RIHS YouTube channel. In specific, according to post-event analysis, the average number of live participants in online training webinars reached 100 participants, coming from more than 70 countries on 6 continents. The participants are researchers

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and/or teaching staff of all levels, practitioners, and officers, as well as many PhD, postgraduate and undergraduate students. They have different backgrounds and study/work/specialize in various disciplines in the field of heritage science.

The in-person events of HS Academy are organized for approximately 20-30 participants at a time. The focus and interests of the audience vary from one event to the other. For instance, Doctoral summer schools are attended mainly by PhD students, while on-site Training Camps by participants of various expertise levels. The in-person events are sometimes held in a hybrid form and increase the accessibility of the theoretical part of the training (provided always in English) to an even wider audience.

E-RIHS will monitor the changes and the evolution of the audience across time and modify the strategy and messages accordingly. For the moment, E-RIHS decided to use a confidential and friendly tone of voice to better inspire and motivate people in the study and protection of heritage.

E-RIHS is also trying to know its analogous and create an alliance with them. For example, E-RIHS has active collaboration with other SSH research infrastructures such as CESSDA, CLARIN, DARIAH, OPERAS, SHARE, and EHRI. Together with them, E-RIHS is participating in an European cluster for sharing experiences, skills, and events and reinforcing its services. Joint communication activities are increasing E-RIHS visibility in the RIs framework.

Depending on the context and the target, E-RIHS will spread key messages that will be built around some key concepts: protection of heritage, heritage science, innovation, and the new generation.

1.5 Branding E-RIHS

Created in 2017 as a visual translation of the multidisciplinary community of researchers and users in the field of heritage science, the E-RIHS logo was registered as a trademark in Europe, Canada, US, Brazil, Peru and Argentina in 2019. The registration guaranteed the protection of the brand identity of E-RIHS and set the basis for a consistent communication strategy.

The E-RIHS logo consists of three elements:

- the icon
- the wordmark
- the payoff.

The logo is described in detail in the E-RIHS brand guidelines (see Annex 1).

1.5.1 A note on licensing

The use of the E-RIHS logo is subject to authorization via email to: co@e-rihs.eu

Each NN has a customized logo, composed of:

- logo E-RIHS
- dot
- country code

The country code (.it, .fr, etc.) must be written in lowercase letters, in full red text using the font Montserrat, and it must have the right proportions: the size of the country code should not be higher than the E-RIHS name in capital letters, as described in the E-RIHS brand guidelines.

1.5.2 E-RIHS brand guidelines

A comprehensive visual identity has been developed based on the logo to ensure consistent and impactful communication, as described in the document “E-RIHS brand guidelines”. It is the essential reference document for all communication from and to the E-RIHS community and aims at preserving the E-RIHS identity, making it recognizable and reinforcing the E-RIHS reputation.

The E-RIHS brand guidelines are primarily addressed to the E-RIHS NNs (and observers) and to the media. Each E-RIHS NN is a part of E-RIHS and shares responsibilities to ensure the correct use of the brand and visual identity (logo, colours, etc). As such, it is encouraged to use them to maintain a clear affiliation between E-RIHS and its activities.

The key rule to adopt in creating communication materials is that “all the E-RIHS communication digital and printed materials should carry the E-RIHS logo and adopt the style defined in the E-RIHS brand guidelines (in terms of fonts and colours)”.

The E-RIHS brand guidelines (Annex 1) define:

- the typography and the colour palette
- the main lockup of the E-RIHS logo and the usage rules
- the HS Academy logo and its usage
- the HS platforms logos and their usage
- the templates (for social media, presentations, brochures, roll-up).

1.6 Promoting E-RIHS

1.6.1 The slogan

In 2020, ESFRI launched its slogan: “Making science happen”. Following this launch, E-RIHS started thinking about which words could recall the ESFRI concept and at the same time tailor it in the field of heritage science.

In November 2023, a survey was launched through social media to ask the HS community to choose the slogan to represent the essence of E-RIHS. The choice was composed of three options:

- E-RIHS | Connecting heritage to science
- E-RIHS | Your gateway to heritage science excellence
- E-RIHS | Exploring the frontier of heritage science

The HS community chose “E-RIHS | Connecting heritage to science”. The slogan can be used as an umbrella concept to promote E-RIHS in communication materials (newsletters, publications, banners for email, etc.) giving evidence to the E-RIHS spirit.

1.6.2 Promoting hashtags

Following the ESFRI and RI-VIS suggestions for communication, E-RIHS has also identified the hashtags to promote its content via social media and amplify its impact on the internet community:

Table 1: Promoting hashtags

	ESFRI	E-RIHS
FOR GENERAL PURPOSE	#EU_RIs	#e-rihs
	#RI_Eu	#ERIHS
	#ResearchInfrastructure	

TO PROMOTE OUR RESEARCH FIELD	#heritagescience
TO COMMUNICATE YOUR CUTTING-EDGE SERVICES, FACILITIES AND RESOURCES	#makesciencehappen #HSAcademy #HSAcademyday #CTinHS #CurrentTopicsinHeritageScience #ERIHSconference #ERIHSsurvey #ERIHSCommunity
TO PROMOTE OPEN SCIENCE	#HeritageScienceGateway #HeritageScienceCommunity

Monitoring hashtags will help to accelerate the growth and connections on social media and build a solid network to circulate information on services and activities.

1.7 Tools and channels

E-RIHS is a distributed and large research infrastructure. To reach this large audience, E-RIHS adopts a wide range of channels and tools to spread news and messages, that are adapted depending on the audience they are aimed at.

Table 2: E-RIHS tools and channels

CHANNEL	TOOLS
VERBAL	meetings in person, face-to-face conversations, interviews (radio, tv), podcasts, phone calls, conferences, exhibitions and fairs, roundtables, etc.
WRITTEN (TRADITIONAL)	letters, reports, presentations, press releases, newspapers
VISUAL	videos, photos, promotional materials (brochures, posters, cards, gadgets, etc.)
DIGITAL	emails, instant messaging apps, website, social media, webinars, online meetings, videos, photos, newsletter, intranet, etc.

1.7.1 Email

E-RIHS uses two email addresses:

Central office – co@e-rihs.eu

Communication office – communication@e-rihs.eu

It is a best practice to follow the rule of including the name of E-RIHS in the subject of the email as follows:

Subject: [E-RIHS] – subject

E-RIHS can count on a consolidated mailing list (elaborated in accordance with GDPR), that can be used for different occasions to spread news and events.

1.7.2 E-RIHS website

In 2023, E-RIHS launched the new website (www.e-rihs.eu), designed to facilitate the exploration and access to news and services. The website also serves as a platform to share training opportunities and resources, provide insights into the E-RIHS governance and structure, and foster new collaborations.

The website is composed of different sections. “About” is the section which tells the story and the governance of the research infrastructure. “Resources” gives access to E-RIHS services (Catalogue of Services, HS academy, etc.), “Newsroom” is the link with E-RIHS events, stories and results, while “Participate” is the section with information for individuals or organizations to become an E-RIHS supporter or member.

The menu item “Catalogue of Services” refers to a stand-alone platform that is currently under construction and will be released at the end of 2024.

Figure 2: Screenshot of the E-RIHS homepage

In the near future, E-RIHS should contemplate also designing a separate platform for HS Academy, similar to what other research infrastructures have already accomplished, to collect training activities and resources.

The website uses a WordPress CMS and a customized Divi theme. A handbook provides step-by-step guidance to support the CMS managers on how to set out the elements to manage contents and provides advice on the implementation and management of the features.

1.7.3 Social media

In 2019, EMMRI conducted an analysis of the digital media landscape for 900 research infrastructures by using their website as data sources. The top five tools used were Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, YouTube and Instagram.

The RI-VIS project conducted a smaller-scale updated of this analysis in 2020, followed by IPERION HS in 2022. Both updates confirmed the continued preference for the same top five tools. E-RIHS also prefers them. In 2017, E-RIHS opened its website and social media accounts on Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube.

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These accounts play a key role in reaching a wide audience, composed of very different types of followers, ranging from young researchers to experts. Consequently, different approaches are employed to effectively reach these distinct groups. To all, E-RIHS strives to deliver messages that are “professional yet human, complete yet concise, sincere yet positive” (footnote: digital style guide 2020, p.11 ss).

To make messages recognizable, E-RIHS has defined visual templates and a simplified use of the logo.

Figure 3: Simplified logo for social media

Table 3: E-RIHS social media numbers

1.7.4 Slack community

The E-RIHS communication officer is an active participant in the Slack “Research Infrastructure Communicators” community (ri-comms.slack.com). Slack serves as a platform for communication officers to share their experiences, ask questions, promote events, and establish connections with other research infrastructures’ initiatives.

1.7.5 Digital communication toolkit

A comprehensive digital communication toolkit has been developed, which includes files and rules for creating communication materials. The toolkit consists of the following components:

- E-RIHS brand guidelines
- E-RIHS logo in different formats
- HS Academy logo in different formats
- E-RIHS platforms logos in different formats

- Template for presentation
- E-RIHS letterhead
- Brochure
- Roll-up.

The digital communication toolkit has been distributed to the NNs. Each NN has its logo, and potentially its website and social media platforms. The NNs can customize the files in the toolkit by adding their country code.

Upon request, a WordPress template is available to create the NNs' websites, ensuring consistency with the E-RIHS ERIC website. The NNs' website can be personalised, but they must adhere to certain fundamental rules, including:

- Correct usage of the E-RIHS logo
- Addition of the country code on the right of the logo (by using the font Monserrat) in lowercase e in full red
- Use of the E-RIHS colour palette
- Inclusion of a link to the E-RIHS ERIC website.

Regarding the NNs' logo, the websites should respect the following:

- The position for the logo is in the top left-hand corner
- The logo should not be animated or have states or scripted interactions
- The correct proportion of the logo must be respected
- The logo must appear on all web pages.

In addition to the above, the NNs' websites should also contain:

- Information about E-RIHS.eu and the contribution of the NN to the project
- Information about the NN itself (mission, participants, areas of research, etc.)
- Presentation of the services offered by the NN and facilities
- News and events related to E-RIHS at national and international level.

It is advisable for the NNs' websites to be bilingual, featuring the national language and English.

DISSEMINATION, OPEN SCIENCE AND CITIZEN SCIENCE

1.1 Objectives

ESFRI supports the development of a European Open Science Cloud and encourages research infrastructures to connect with EOSC, promoting open science practices to share research data and contributing to interdisciplinary research. In this dynamic digital landscape, E-RIHS actively engages with the EOSC challenges, playing multiple roles as a data producer, service provider, and final user. E-RIHS is helping the scientific community to define a robust Open Science strategy for heritage science and in doing so it is collaborating with other SSH research infrastructures (DARIAH, CLARIN, OPERAS, EHRI, DiSSCO).

Open Science practices in E-RIHS aim to accelerate the circulation of ideas and research outputs and foster innovation in the field of heritage science. E-RIHS is committed to creating a FAIR ecosystem for services and data and is aligning its tools with international interoperability standards for data sharing. To promote a FAIR culture among users and providers, recommendations will be drafted, and some training initiatives will be organized.

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The E-RIHS Catalogue of Services and access procedures have already been aligned with the Open Science best practices and the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA).

The main objectives of the dissemination activities are to maximise the impact of the E-RIHS research community on various audiences in different fields:

- scientific community
- cultural and creative sectors and industries
- funders and investors
- society.

1.7.6 Open access publishing

E-RIHS encourages the publication of its achievements through open access peer-reviewed journals. However, the final decision to publish is taken once the results are fully evaluated and intellectual property rights protected. Different, inclusive practices of open access publication are used: (i) green open access, also through online self-archiving, possibly in the Zenodo E-RIHS community, and (ii) gold open access, where access to scientific papers is made open by publishers themselves. Each publication includes bibliographic metadata that are released under the CC0 licence.

1.7.7 Acknowledgment publications

All E-RIHS communication and dissemination materials must include the following acknowledgement:

This research has been conducted/funded/supported by E-RIHS ERIC (European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science)

The inclusion of a disclaimer is crucial in enabling the data harvesting systems to automatically retrieve research products and link them to the E-RIHS community in the heritage science gateway (see the “tool” section) and in other web semantic portals.

As E-RIHS is supported by ESFRI, which serves as a strategic instrument for fostering the scientific integration of Europe, E-RIHS can highlight its support in all relevant events and materials.

1.7.8 Tools

1.7.8.1 OpenAIRE Connect and Monitor

In partnership with OpenAIRE, E-RIHS has activated a Connect gateway that focused on “Heritage Science”: <https://heritage-science.openaire.eu/>, a collaborative platform to ease sharing, linking, disseminating and monitoring the research products of the heritage science and E-RIHS community. This platform is particularly valuable for an interdisciplinary community like heritage science, as it brings together scientific publications, datasets and research outcomes produced in very different disciplines; physicists, chemists, archaeologists, restorers, paleoanthropologists, etc., can be easily updated on different topics and results simply by browsing the gateway. A user can join the gateway, upload and link publications to the community and funding, and share results.

As of January 2024, the gateway already includes 10.126 publications, 924 research data, 33 research software, and 952 other research products. Following a joint launch by E-RIHS and OpenAIRE on social media on January 12, 2024, researchers from around the world started joining the community.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the Heritage Science gateway

The gateway is connected with another OpenAIRE tool: Monitor (<https://monitor.openaire.eu/dashboard/heritage-science>). The platform tracks and highlights trends and the impact of research in heritage science. This can help E-RIHS to better promote innovative research pathways within the community.

Table 1: Overview of the Heritage Science Monitor Tool

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1.7.8.2 Zenodo community

Zenodo is a repository for publications and datasets, developed and operated by CERN and OpenAIRE. In 2020, E-RIHS joined Zenodo and created a community to upload research and outreach products (<https://www.zenodo.org/communities/e-rihs/?page=1&size=20>). The Zenodo community allows the heritage science gateway to automatically gather data and integrate them into OpenAIRE.

1.7.8.3 Digital tools for data management

E-RIHS inherited a space on GitHub (<https://github.com/E-RIHS>) to explore methods to improve interoperability across heritage science data. This digital space includes dynamic models, JSON form editors and validators, and proposals for storing gathered metadata. The system is developing a FAIR approach to data and their reuse in heritage science.

- E-RIHS IP set up a collaboration platform (<https://e-rihs.io>) to act as a central hub for E-RIHS-related digital services and information. Initially, it starts by listing the wide range of useful digital services/systems/resources/software. At the moment, the following tools were set up:

- <https://data.e-rihs.io/> – a CORDRA open-source account for gathering metadata for E-RIHS and to create a database underneath other web system such as the E-RIHS service catalogue
- <https://vocab.e-rihs.io/opentheso2/?idc=289&idt=th1> – A Opentheso tool to build the E-RIHS vocabularies and controlled lists for the E-RIHS service catalogue. A working group started to discuss options at: <https://github.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability/tree/main/Vocabulary>

Further details can be read in the living document of the E-RIHS Data Management Plan.

1.7.9 Citizen science

What does “citizen science” mean? The European Commission defines “citizen science” as the general public’s active “engagement in scientific research activities when citizens actively contribute to science, either with their intellectual effort or surrounding knowledge or with their tools and resources. Participants provide experimental data and facilities for researchers, raise new questions, and co-create a new scientific culture”. Citizen science can be considered a bridge between science and society. Citizen science is a collaborative process. Citizen science aims to bring advancements in scientific research outputs and impacts as well as increase the public's understanding of science.

EU projects illustrate how research infrastructures are actively involved in promoting and supporting citizen science initiatives across various domains, including climate action, heritage science, and cultural heritage enrichment. Research infrastructures encourage citizen participation in their projects by adopting some smart strategies such as enriching data and creating new ecosystems, open their datasets and fostering collaboration and innovation. The participation of citizens can lead to increased engagement and collaboration in scientific research and innovation. E-RIHS can develop multiple ideas related to CS activities.

Citizen science can play a key role in disseminating E-RIHS activities. E-RIHS combines science with innovation with a strong impact on society and economy. Starting from the idea of adopting a holistic approach to communication to effectively engage the public and increase its impact on society, we are trying to build a collaborative and interdisciplinary environment around the common issue of the protection of world heritage. If we consider that one of the E-RIHS communication goals is “communicating with people” (see D6.1) and not to people, having interactions online and in-person for developing long-term relationships and creating consistent outcomes, we can see how citizen science can be complementary to communication to reach different targets.

Citizen science can be applied to cultural heritage, engaging the public in various aspects of cultural heritage research and preservation. This collaborative approach allows non-professionals to contribute to the documentation, conservation, and understanding of cultural artefacts and sites. It can encompass activities such as data collection, digitization, and monitoring of cultural heritage resources. The involvement of citizens in cultural heritage initiatives not only enhances public engagement and awareness but also contributes to the advancement of research and the protection of cultural heritage for future generations.

Citizen science can be used to preserve cultural heritage through various means, including data collection, monitoring of volunteers, and community engagement. By involving the public in the documentation and conservation of heritage sites and artefacts, citizen science not only enhances public awareness and engagement but also contributes to the generation of reliable data for monitoring and preserving heritage sites. Additionally, citizen science initiatives can lead to the development of digital platforms that unify scattered efforts and collective knowledge, further contributing to the preservation of cultural heritage. The engagement of diverse stakeholder communities, including students, researchers, and heritage enthusiasts, can also lead to the development and testing of new methods and activities, ultimately fostering a sense of shared responsibility for preserving cultural heritage. The table below showcases some successful experiences:

E-RIHS can approach citizen science:

Deliverable D6.2

- to create a working group to develop citizen science practices
- to implement the DIGILAB platform with creating digital libraries, cataloguing and analyzing data, training AI models for semantic data interpretation, etc. (e.g. taking inspiration from [The Smithsonian Transcription Center](#) experience or [The Lives of Literary Characters project](#))
- to actively engage citizens in the co-creation of knowledge and in the protection of cultural heritage at national, European, and global level.

Researchers are not necessarily equipped with the essential skills to effectively plan a citizen science project. There are many online training resources that can be adapted to this scope focusing on the E-RIHS researchers' needs.

- The IMPETUS project – It will support and give recognition to citizen science by enabling a wider range of Citizen Science Initiatives (CSIs) to access innovative funding (2022-2026): <https://impetus4cs.eu/>
- The eu-citizen.science platform – Funded by the EU, it offers online training modules on the Moodle platform (2022-2026): <https://moodle.eu-citizen.science>
- The Parthenos project – It developed a citizen science toolkit to build a project (2020): <https://training.parthenos-project.eu/sample-page/citizen-science-in-the-digital-arts-and-humanities/>
- LiberEurope – The LIBER (Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries) is the voice of Europe's research library community. It drafted a citizen science guide in 2 sections. Section 1 (2021): <https://libereurope.eu/document/citizen-science-guide-section-1-citizen-science-skilling-for-library-staff-researchers-and-the-public/guide/> and Section 2 (2023): <https://libereurope.eu/document/citizen-science-guide-section-2-library-infrastructures-and-citizen-science/library-infrastructures-citizen-science/>
- Harvard College – It drafted a manual that aims to empower individuals in their roles as citizen scientists and promote the practice of community-based citizen science as a vehicle for environmental justice (2019): <https://citizenscienceguide.com/homepage>
- CitizenScience.gov – It is an official government website designed to accelerate the use of crowdsourcing and citizen science across the U.S. government. They created a toolkit to show five basic process steps for planning, designing and carrying out a crowdsourcing or citizen science project (2019): <https://www.citizenscience.gov/toolkit/#>
- The National Geographic Society – It offers a free online course: “Learning through Citizen Science”. It takes 5 hours to introduce global citizen science and its potential for teaching and learning. The course, composed of three modules, is available at the following link: <https://account.nationalgeographic.org/courses/cit-sci-home>
- The ZOOuniverse – is a platform for people-powered research that gives people of all ages and backgrounds the chance to participate in real research with over 50 active online citizen science projects in different domains. It is possible to build a project on the platform and share it. The platform, funded by private institutions, is available at the following link: <https://www.zooniverse.org/>

1.7.10 E-RIHS events and training activities

Several types of events organized/participated by E-RIHS will disseminate achievements and will be used for outreach to potential users and industry. Success stories, project results and best practices will be presented at focused events, workshops, through the user forum, in training camps, and summer schools. Conferences attended by partners disseminating scientific activities or setting up conference exhibition stands will be the

staple of dissemination activities. Events will be promoted using social media, the user forum, web tools, and when practical, video streamed.

The E-RIHS annual event could be the time to present contributions from the community on specific themes defined time by time. Submission calls can be launched to collect candidates to present finished or ongoing work related to the annual theme. The call accepts papers, panels, poster and demos.

The HS Academy is the umbrella terms under which E-RIHS provides training online and in-person opportunities. HS Academy organizes different type of initiatives (webinar, lecture, doctoral summer school, training camp, etc.), that are incredible opportunities to disseminate research results and help researchers from different domains meet and discuss new approaches to heritage science.

E-RIHS is working to implement the HS Academy structure and giving it a formal framework in collaboration with other research infrastructures, the universities and research institutes. The experience of other research infrastructures, described in the document available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/7844538>, suggests creating a web space dedicated to training activities, to target training opportunities, and to open a helpdesk to reinforce the connection with the heritage science community.

EXPLOITATION STRATEGY

On the basis for the long-term sustainability of E-RIHS ERIC, the formulation of an adequate exploitation strategy is key and unfolds in different action areas. First, the Commission staff working document “Long-term sustainability of Research Infrastructures” highlights the importance of better exploiting the data generated to improve research replicability and efficiency, strengthen innovation, develop new activities and boost the productivity and competitiveness of the European industry. Additionally, this document establishes, among other relevant actions, the following:

- i. to unlock the innovation potential aiming at identifying technical areas of interest for industrial research,
- ii. to ensure scientific excellence and socio-economic impact, aiming at stimulating R&I and concentrate human capital, and
- iii. to focus on training programmes aiming at fully exploiting instrumentation and expert knowledge.

Below, we describe the strategy formulated to exploit the potential of E-RIHS ERIC in providing solutions to the heritage science and societal ecosystems. This strategy builds upon E-RIHS IP D6.1 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication, developed within task T6.2, and previous documents from IPERION HS and E-RIHS PP projects aiming at the same goals.

1.8 E-RIHS Innovation and Exploitation ecosystem

Societal and industrial innovation is at the core of all E-RIHS activities, which support research on heritage interpretation, documentation, preservation, and management, from access to cutting-edge laboratories, tools, and data, through strategic partnerships, to the delivery of training opportunities.

E-RIHS is a vibrant ecosystem that produces a variety of innovative products with great potential for exploitation. Its four access platforms, MOLAB, ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, and DIGILAB, in themselves, are an innovative concept that reflects the advance of the state-of-the-art of the heritage science domain, build over time by different EU-funded research infrastructure projects, such as LabS TECH, EU-ARTECH, CHARISMA, IPERION CH, E-RIHS PP and IPERION HS. Apart from those novel and efficient modes of access, a broad range of products and services are also susceptible to exploitation in E-RIHS ERIC including heritage-

led methodologies, new and advanced instrumentation, knowledge spill over-technology transfer, research-based tools, and open data sharing and e-infrastructures for sustainable, open digital archives (Fig. 5).

Figure 5 Most common areas where innovations are made from E-RIHS PP survey

The most effective means of exploiting the innovation that will be generated in E-RIHS ERIC are licensing agreements, establishing new companies, creating joint ventures, and outright sale of innovations. However, there are not so many examples of successful commercialization resulting from the activity of the set of projects mentioned above, which suggests the existence of gaps preventing exploitation and introducing innovation to the market.

To bridge these gaps, that could prevent from efficiently exploiting E-RIHS ERIC innovation, key aspects will be addressed: identification of product potential, definition of an exploitation methodology, identification of markets, inclusion of value chain and profit model analysis, finding resources and key partnerships, and the identification of other needs and potential obstacles and inhibitors. The concrete actions that are proposed aim at identifying, promoting and exploiting E-RIHS innovation potential are detailed below.

1.9 Mechanisms to facilitate effective exploitation

To ensure the long-term sustainability and success of E-RIHS ERIC, exploitation of innovation is key and dependent on an efficient monitoring and evaluation system, the appropriate knowledge and technology transfer channels, the proper protection of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), the development of human resources through training, the engagement with relevant stakeholders of the private and public sectors, and the identification of funding opportunities. This set of actions for effective exploitation is detailed below.

1.9.1 Mapping and monitoring innovation

Major key achievements on instrumentation and technologies, measurement methodologies and protocols, documentation tools and data management procedures, etc. need to be evaluated on a periodic basis as they are constantly evolving, with the critical input (co-creation) of users. A systematic evaluation approach with indicators (KPIs) is required for monitoring the potential of existing ideas and tools, and identifying emerging opportunities for innovation.

Specifically, the effectively move from innovation to exploitation requires the establishment of mechanisms to monitor progress, advice on key research and application areas for development, indicate exploitation opportunities and suggest adjustments when things go wrong. One of those mechanisms to detect emerging opportunities in terms of financing innovation, collaboration opportunities, funding schemes and

encouraging synergies between stakeholders is the “innovation radar” that will be set up in E-RIHS ERIC. The aim of this radar is ‘scan’ the landscape not only within the E-RIHS ecosystem but in a much broader range (e.g. medical diagnostic technologies, automotive and aerospace, construction and buildings sector or forensics and environment) where relevant ideas and technologies grow. In this way, it becomes possible to adapt new tools and methods and introduce them to heritage applications and then exploit them in the heritage marketplace.

The Central Liaison Office for Innovation (CLO), conceptualized as a functional role within the E-RIHS ERIC organization, will support E-RIHS National Node along with associated local Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs) with structured procedures aimed at mapping key achievements, identifying emerging needs, and monitoring innovation. Additionally, the Regional Development Strategies Advisory Board (RDSAB) that is composed of experts appointed by the National Nodes, and set in the framework of IPERION HS project, will contribute to identifying emerging needs.

1.9.2 Specialized management

To properly manage exploitation activities in E-RIHS ERIC, the Central Liaison Office for Innovation (CLO), focusing on communication and coordination, will work alongside with the Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs) of the National Nodes to develop a technology transfer methodology based on enhanced networking among the TTOs. These bodies will properly support the exploitation opportunities and advise the involved parties on the optimal exploitation routes related to business development, market analysis, funding opportunities and IPR management. Furthermore, the CLO will be responsible for setting up and updating the innovation monitoring mechanisms aforementioned, will facilitate collaborations and enable contacts of the interested parties with investors, will organize special events, and will design a strategic communication approach.

1.9.3 IPR support system

The implementation strategy for IPR, delivered in E-RIHS PP and IPERION HS, is crucial to enable the industrial or commercial exploitation of E-RIHS’ products and services from in-house research or in cooperation, while recognising the contributions of individuals, their organisation, and those of any other parties. A well-defined and balanced IP support system, adjustable to the different types of innovations, and related to national and EU legal and administrative framework as well as guidelines of international organisations, enables the transformation of innovation into societal benefits and promotes creativity. TTOs will hold responsibility for appropriate IPR management, for establishing collaboration with industry and other stakeholders, for facilitating exploitation of the broad research outcomes (e.g. via the creation of spin-offs), for providing information on opportunities for private and/or public funding, and for training of the research and scientific community on technology transfer procedures.

1.9.4 Data services

Within E-RIHS ERIC, the exploitation of digital research work is at its core and ensuring better availability, access and interoperability is crucial in enabling data and digital objects (including tools, protocols, algorithms, etc.) to be shared and used for research, innovation and education across different systems and platforms.

Within E-RIHS PP, the policy framework for data curation in the context of heritage science, based on open science practices and FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) was established. Data management principles were further developed in IPERION HS Data Management Plan (DMP) and currently in the DMP for E-RIHS ERIC due in M20.

Deliverable D6.2

The exploitation of different types of data or digital objects and related metadata will be built on the development of digital services and processes (vocabulary server, persistent identifier (PID) system, repository for aggregation of metadata, etc.) set up by E-RIHS Central Hub with the support of E-RIHS IP WP5, in charge of starting the first iteration of the DIGILAB digital service platform.

1.9.5 Engaging the diverse user community

Heritage science is a highly interdisciplinary and fragmented ecosystem with significant number of stakeholders including museums, galleries, archives, commercial companies from the cultural and creative sectors, private companies of conservators and restorers, neighbouring RIs, etc. with capacity to actively participate in the innovation chain of E-RIHS ERIC. They can contribute to new knowledge, enhance access services, become providers, promote new infrastructures, identify new research areas, provide commercialisation and training opportunities, (co-)design instrumentation, create business incubation units and partnerships, increase visibility of RI, etc.

It is therefore crucial to improve mutual cooperation, identify and engage new user communities (e.g. media, mental wellbeing and others) that can contribute to E-RIHS scientific strategy as co-creators. The establishment of regular connections (e.g. by establishing a User Forum, through meetings, consultations, co-creation labs, HS Academy, etc.) will nurture their expertise and will help strengthen and diversify the opportunities for their involvement as active collaborators in research and innovation. The community cohesion will undoubtedly benefit the whole heritage science domain at European and global level by facilitating effective exploitation of current and potential technological, social and cultural innovation.

1.9.6 Training

E-RIHS ERIC ambition is the promotion of innovation across the spectrum of its research activities. To strengthen and capitalizing on this innovation, and bringing it from the laboratories to the heritage marketplace, the training of access providers, infrastructure managers, and users is crucial.

Appropriate specialized training on different issues such as technology transfer, digital tools, scientific techniques, etc. will rely on the HS Academy and the development of closer links with existing providers of HS education. These activities will promote the commercialization of products and services by fully exploiting RI instrumentation and expert knowledge. For the development of key skills and competences, doctoral summer schools for emerging heritage scientists, onsite training camps, webinar series, online training modules, user conferences etc. will be made available on all levels of training. The revised E-RIHS Training Strategy will be delivered in M21.

1.9.7 Funding

Funding is a key element to exploit ideas and research results in the heritage marketplace with a social and economic value. Commercial exploitation of the outcomes of the RI can leverage initial investment and lead to creation of new companies and jobs. Furthermore, preserving heritage and enhancing its enjoyment benefits the general public and impacts the revenues of cultural tourism and cultural institutions.

E-RIHS Central Hub, TTOs and RDSAB will scout funding opportunities at regional, national or European level from public and private sectors. For the development of the RI at regional level, the Research & Innovation Smart Specialisation Strategies (RIS3) will be a key instrument in terms of socio-economic return by stimulating research and innovation and concentrating human capital. While industry, understood here as anyone outside of pure academia with revenue/commercial potential, will play a crucial role as user, partner, and (funding) supplier (of instrumentation, related services, commercial procurements, etc.). To address the financial sustainability of the RI, a new revised and updated business plan of E-RIHS will be delivered in M24.

MONITORING AND REPORTING DEC ACTIVITIES

As recommended by ESFRI, E-RIHS has established a series of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to assess the performance of DEC activities. These KPIs are described in the E-RIHS IP deliverable D3.5 E-RIHS Quality System Implementation Plan. Monitoring DEC activities is crucial to evaluate the RI's impact and ensure adherence to the RACER criteria that make them:

- Relevant
- Accepted
- Credible
- Easy to monitor
- Robust.

The evaluation process goes beyond a mere retrospective analysis of past actions; it is a forward-looking process that aims to enhance and guide future DEC activities. The monitoring is not about performance, but mainly about satisfaction of the community. Monitoring provides insights into the behaviour of E-RIHS's audience and help E-RIHS to adopt new approaches. The aim is to communicate, disseminate and exploit the results and activities in a consistent, clear, open, and trustworthy way.

Data will be collected through social media insights tools, website insight tool, and specific forms (e.g. registration forms, attendance certifications, post event surveys, etc.).

E-RIHS monitors the DEC activities periodically and publishes a report yearly, assessing and adjusting its strategy accordingly.

LEARN THE TECHNICAL LANGUAGE: TO BETTER UNDERSTAND THE E-RIHS RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Distributed research infrastructure – is an organization that enables the research community to use specific facilities, resources and services that are geographically scattered.

Physical access – is “hands-on” access when Users physically visit an infrastructure, /facility/ or equipment. The available services or resources are not unlimited, and a competitive process is required following a defined procedure and criteria for selection of Users.

Remote access – is access to resources and services offered by the RI without Users physically visiting the infrastructure/facility. Similar to Physical access, the services or resources are not unlimited, and a competitive selection is required.

Virtual access – means free access to Users provided through communication networks; the available services or resources can be simultaneously used by an unlimited number of Users and the Users are not selected. Virtual access typically concerns access to data and digital tools.

Inputs – what is needed to plan, design, and implement communication (ex-ante evaluation, planning, budgeting)

Outputs – what we deliver that reaches and engages the target audience (reach, exposure, publicity volume, deliverables)

Outcomes/Results – What the target audience takes out of communication. Their initial response and sustainable effects (awareness, recall, engagement, follow-up actions)

Impacts – Behavioural and/or cultural shifts in population directly or partly caused by communication (opinion change towards the EU, advocacy). It describes how the organization’s performance can influence the satisfaction of the interests and needs of all those stakeholders (internal and external to the organization), which are vital for the existence of the organisation itself.

Figure 6: EC communication indicators (2022)

CONCLUSION

E-RIHS ERIC will be a interdisciplinary and distributed research infrastructure. Communicating, disseminating and exploiting the E-RIHS ERIC results will be crucial to create a cohesive community and reinforce the impact on the European Research Area and the society. It will be necessary to frequently re-evaluate the strategy, review the KPIs and monitor the activities.

Success in any endeavour is the result of careful planning, hard work, and dedication. To achieve E-RIHS ERIC goals, it will be important to stay focused, set achievable targets, and remain committed to the task at hand. It will be a responsibility of all E-RIHS community members and the National Nodes will play a fundamental role in creating a collaborative network for sharing and highlighting E-RIHS results.

Only this way, E-RIHS will be the true gateway to connect heritage to science!

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ANNEX 1: E-RIHS brand guidelines

E-RIHS

EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE
FOR HERITAGE SCIENCE

WHAT IS

E-RIHS?

E-RIHS (European Research Infrastructure on Heritage Science) is a pan-European distributed research infrastructure based on advancing and sharing the best research resources available in the field of Heritage Science.

Heritage Science is a trans-disciplinary scientific domain founded on the synergy of knowledge from arts, humanities, science and technology and provides a holistic approach to cultural and natural heritage preservation, documentation, interpretation and management.

INDEX

GENETICS

TYPOGRAPHY

COLOUR

THE BRAND

LOGO

- Main Lockup
- Alternative Lockups
- Positive & Negative

USAGE RULES

- Clear Space
- Minimum Size
- Incorrect Uses
- Use In Images

LOCAL PERSONALIZATION

E-RIHS COMMUNICATION

PLATFORMS

DIGITAL TEMPLATES

- Social
- Presentation

PRINT TEMPLATES

- Brochure
- Roll Up

BRAND FONTS

E-RIHS fonts are Proxima Nova and Libre Franklin. As an alternative to Proxima Nova, the brand will use Montserrat as a system font. (For outputs such as Canvas and Google presentation)

Proxima nova is an Adobe font, Libre Franklin is a Google font both are highly legible and contemporary.

 Download montserrat

 Download libre franklin

Proxima Nova

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee
Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll
Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr
Ss Tt Uu
Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz
0123456789
#!@£\$€%&*()::;?·

SEMIBOLD
BOLD
EXTRABOLD
BLACK

Libre Franklin

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff
Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm
Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt
Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz
0123456789
#!@£\$€%&*()::;?·

REGULAR
ITALIC
SEMIBOLD
SEMIBOLD ITALIC

Montserrat (system font)

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee
Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk
Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp
Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu
Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz
0123456789
#!@£\$€%&*()::;?·

SEMIBOLD
BOLD
EXTRABOLD
BLACK

FONT HIERARCHY

NEWS

da Redazione | Feb 10, 2023 | 0 commenti

THE 2ND IPERION HS ACADEMY TRAINING CAMP WILL BE HELD IN TELČ, CZECH REPUBLIC ON JUNE 26-30, 2023

THE 2ND IPERION HS A CADEMY TRAINING CAMP

In the historic centre of Telč – the UNESCO World Heritage Site. The Institute of Theoretical and Applied Mechanics of the Czech Academy of Sciences (ITAM CAS) is organizing the 2nd IPERION HS Academy Training Camp, which will be held at the Centre Telč of ITAM CAS (Telč, Czech Republic) from June 26 to June 30, 2023. This on-site camp will offer the experience of working with the complexity of built heritage and will introduce the participants to cutting-edge tools for diagnostics and methods of investigation.

CATEGORIES HASHTAGS

Proxima Nova Bold
Letter spacing 25pt

ACCENTS

Libre Franklin Regular
Letter spacing 0pt

HEADING 1

Proxima Nova Extrabold
All Caps | Letter spacing 0pt

SUB HEADING

Proxima Nova bold
All Caps | Letter spacing 0pt

BODYTEXT

LibreFranklin Regular
Letter spacing 0pt

TEXT DINAMIC

LibreFranklin Semibold
Libre Franklin Italic

COLOUR PALETTE

E-RIHS RED

CMYK 0 · 86 · 81 · 8
 RGB 234 · 33 · 45
 #EA212D

DARK BEIGE

CMYK 0 · 4 · 10 · 13
 RGB 221 · 212 · 198
 #DDD4C6

LIGHT GREY

CMYK 0 · 0 · 0 · 15
 RGB 217 · 217 · 217
 #D9D9D9

E-RIHS BLUE

CMYK 60 · 38 · 0 · 59
 RGB 42 · 65 · 105
 #2A4169

E-RIHS WHITE

CMYK 0 · 0 · 0 · 3
 RGB 247 · 246 · 246
 #F7F6F6

YELLOW

CMYK 0 · 30 · 76 · 5
 RGB 242 · 170 · 57
 #F2AA39

LIGHT BLUE

CMYK 34 · 0 · 3 · 18
 RGB 137 · 208 · 202
 #89D0CA

LIGHT GREEN

CMYK 13 · 0 · 40 · 12
 RGB 195 · 224 · 134
 #C3E086

BEIGE

CMYK 0 · 4 · 11 · 0
 RGB 228 · 218 · 204
 #E4DACC

FIXLAB

MOLAB

ARCHLAB

DIGILAB

INSTITUTIONAL COLOURS

E-RIHS has one main colour, red, that is complemented by dark beige, light grey and blue forming the primary colours of the brand. These colours must be used for **general and institutional communications**, such as news, events and others.

In addition, white is used as neutral colors to balance the other institutional brand colours.

PLATFORM COLOURS

Within E-RIHS there are four main access platforms:

- ARCHLAB
- MOLAB
- FIXLAB
- DIGILAB

To differentiate their activities within E-RIHS and separate them from E-RIHS institutional communication, each platform will be identified by one colour that composes the logo's symbol and therefore composes E-RIHS.

MAIN LOCKUP

E-RIHS logo consists of three elements. The icon, the wordmark and the payoff. The full logo should only appear in full colour or grayscale. Both follow the same usage rules, such as minimum size.

In no way should the logo be modified, redrawn and distorted.

The logo is protected as a trademark in Europe, US, BR, PE, Canada and Argentina. The use of the logo must be required and supervised by the Communications Office.

SECONDARY LOGO

The secondary logos have **very restrictive usage**. It can **only** be employed in **social media** where the main logo cannot fit the layout.

The secondary logos guarantee E-RIHS visibility social media communication without compromising the brand recognizability and it's aesthetic nature.

LOGO WORDMARK + PAYOFF VERTICAL LOCKUP

LOGO WORDMARK + SYMBOL SIMPLIFIED

THE BRAND
LOGO

POSITIVE & NEGATIVE

LOGO - MAIN LOCKUP

LOGO - SOCIAL MEDIA ALTERNATIVES

THE BRAND USAGE RULES

The rules demonstrated here are valid the logos lockups and must always be respected.

LOGO CLEAR SPACE

To ensure the right breathing space for the logo follow the following steps:

- STEP 1:** → **STEP 2:** → **STEP 3:**
- Pick the letter "E" → Rotate it 90° → Use the height to create the logo clear space

MINIMUM SPACE

Minimum size
4,0 cm

Minimum size
100 px

SCALING

THE BRAND
USAGE RULES

The rules demonstrated here are valid the logos lockups and must **always** be respected.

INCORRECT LOGO USAGE

Do not alter the symbol

Do not change the proportion of the elements
Do not eliminate elements from the logo

Do not re-arrange the elements of the logo

Do not use a colour outside from the institucional colour palette

THE BRAND
USAGE RULES

USE IN IMAGES

The logotype should always be visible and not lost on busy backgrounds and textures.

If the legibility of the logo is ever compromised create a colour box on top of the image to place the logo.

THE BRAND
**NATIONAL
PERSONALIZATION**

NATIONAL LOGO

The logo must be used locally and it should be customised at a national level. Next to the name E-RIHS is added a dot and the abbreviation of the regional branch in **lower case**, alluding to the website.

For example, E-RIHS.fr is allowed, but 'E-RIHS.FRANCE', 'E-RIHS.FR', 'E-RIHS.Île-de-France' cannot be used.

The addition must appear in **Montserrat Extra Bold**.

For all national usage, regardless of location, the logo must respect all of its rules of usage (minimum size, colour...).

- The Wordmark must be in the brand's red.
- The payoff must be in dark beige.
- The Symbol cannot be altered.
- The composition cannot be altered.

*A branch personalization file with an editable logo and font will be provided to each regional office where E-RIHS is currently active.

INCORRECT LOGO USAGE

THE BRAND

HS

ACADEMY

HS ACADEMY LOGO

IPERION HS established the HS Academy, that gathers the training opportunities for the community: Training Camp, Doctoral Summer School, Webinar, Lecture, and Training modules.

The HS Academy logo consists of two elements: the icon and the wordmark.

The logo has one main colour: blue.

The font is Montserrat.

E-RIHS BLUE

CMYK 60 · 38 · 0 · 59
RGB 42 · 65 · 105
#2A4169

POSITIVE & NEGATIVE

LOGO - MAIN LOCKUP

E-RIHS

COMMUNICATION

E-RIHS IS MADE UP OF FOUR ACCESS PLATFORMS:

FIXLAB

FIXED LABORATORIES

Access to large-scale and medium-scale facilities for sophisticated scientific investigations on samples or whole objects, revealing their microstructure and chemical composition, giving essential and invaluable insights into historical technologies, materials, alteration and degradation phenomena or authenticity.

MOLAB

MOBILE LABORATORIES

Access to an impressive array of advanced mobile analytical instrumentation for non-invasive measurements on valuable or immovable objects, archaeological sites and historical monuments. The Mobile LABORatory allows its users to implement complex multi-technique diagnostic projects, permitting the most effective in situ investigations.

ARCHLAB

ARCHIVES

Access to specialized knowledge and organized scientific information – including technical images, analytical data and conservation documentation – in datasets largely unpublished from archives of prestigious European museums, galleries and research institutions.

DIGILAB

DIGITAL DATA AND TOOLS

Virtual access to scientific data concerning tangible heritage, making them FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). It includes searchable registries of multidimensional images, analytical data and documentation from large academic as well as research and heritage institutions

CANVA ACCOUNT FOR SOCIAL MEDIA

To create the visuals for social media and use the models for E-RIHS, it is necessary to sign in in Canva and follow the links:

- Facebook post
- Stories
- Instagram

If you don't have an account, you can create a new one for free at the follow link:
<https://www.canva.com/>

E-RIHS
EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE HUB FOR HIGH-RESOLUTION IMAGING

PRESENTATION TITLE

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E-RIHS

TITLE

SUBTITLE

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www.e-rihs.eu

E-RIHS

TITLE SECTION

www.e-rihs.eu

E-RIHS

TITLE

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www.e-rihs.eu

E-RIHS

INTERNAL TITLE

SOTTOTITOLO
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www.e-rihs.eu

E-RIHS

TITLE

Option 1
Option 2
Option 3

www.e-rihs.eu

MOLAB

TITLE SECTION MOLAB

E-RIHS

TITLE

SUBTITLE

HIGHLIGHTS
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.

Timeline diagram showing a sequence of events over time.

www.e-rihs.eu

FIXLAB

SECTION TITLE FIXLAB

FIXLAB

**FIXED
LABORATORIES**

Access to large-scale equipment for scale facilities for complex related investigations on samples and whole objects.

ARCHLAB

ARCHIVES

Access to specialized knowledge and organized scientific information on objects largely unpublished from prestigious archives.

MOBLAB

**MOBILE
LABORATORIES**

Access to flexible and mobile analytical instrumentation for non-invasive measurements on movable or immovable objects.

DIGILAB

**DIGITAL DATA
AND TOOLS**

Virtual access to scientific data concerning long-term flows, making them FAIR (Findable-Accessible-Interoperable-Reusable).

WHAT DOES
E-RIHS DO?

WE PROVIDE SERVICES

E-RIHS offers access to its 4 platforms, shares scientific resources and knowledge, promotes joint research activities.

WE EDUCATE

E-RIHS organizes training and mobility of researchers and advances the development of innovative academic curricula in heritage science.

WE CONNECT PEOPLE

E-RIHS promotes the synergy of cooperation among academics, research centers and cultural institutions.

WHAT IS
E-RIHS?

E-RIHS is on the way to become a pan-European distributed Research Infrastructure based on scientific and sharing the best cross-disciplinary resources available in the field of Heritage Science.

DO YOU HAVE QUESTIONS ABOUT
E-RIHS AND ITS SERVICES?
WWW.E-RIHS.EU | CO@E-RIHS.EU

**FIXED
LABORATORIES**

Access to large-scale and medium-scale facilities for sophisticated investigations on samples and whole objects.

ARCHIVES

Access to specialised knowledge and organized scientific information dataset largely unpublished from prestigious archives.

**MOBILE
LABORATORIES**

Access to advanced mobile analytical instrumentation for non-invasive measurements on movable or immovable art objects.

**DIGITAL DATA
AND TOOLS**

Virtual access to scientific data concerning tangible heritage, making them FAIR (Findable-Accessible-Interoperable-Reusable).

E-RIHS
European Research Infrastructure for High-Resolution Imaging Science

¿Quieres saber más sobre el proyecto?
Proyecto financiado por el Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación

Logo of the European Union, the Spanish government, and the E-RIHS project.

HAVE YOU ANY QUESTIONS
ON E-RIHS OR ITS SERVICES?
WWW.E-RIHS.EU | CO@E-RIHS.EU

 E-RIHS
EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE
FOR HERITAGE SCIENCE

 E-RIHS
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PHOTO CREDITS: LOREM IPSUM

MOLAB

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